

Effects of variable parameters on physical properties of unfinished Single Jersey Knit Fabric

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Abstract Single jersey unfinished cotton weft knitted (loop formation) fabrics tend to undergo a certain dimensional changes due to changeable yarn count (N_e) and variable stitch length on physical properties such as Shrinkage, Spirality, Bursting Strength, Pilling, GSM, (Gram per square meter). This study is founded on unfinished knit cloth where yarn counts recycled remained $24N_e$, $28N_e$, $30N_e$ for S/J. Single jersey unfinished cotton fabrics were produced with different count and with stitch length where it is found that for constant count, increase of the Stitch Length the GSM is decreased & for constant stitch length, increase of the count GSM is decreased. Used for constant stitch length, increase of the count the Bursting strength is decreased. Designed for constant count, by increase of stitch length the length wise shrinkage% is decreased & the fabric length is increased. Used for constant stitch length, by increase of the count the length wise shrinkage % is decreased & the fabric length is increased. Aimed at constant count, by increase of the stitch length the width wise shrinkage% is improved & the cloth thickness is reduced. Intended for constant stitch length, by increase of the count the width wise shrinkage% is improved & the cloth width is reduced. Used aimed at constant count, by increase of the stitch length the spirality% is increased. Aimed at constant stitch length, by increase of the count the spirality % is increased.

Keywords: Yarn Count, unfinished S/J fabric; Stitch length, Spirality, Shrinkage; GSM, Count, Bursting Strength, Pilling etc.

Introduction

Knitting is a development of cloth starting by the joining the loops of yarns. When single loop is drawn through additional, twists continue formed in parallel or perpendicular direction[1]. Knitted cloth is a textile that consequences from knitting, the procedure of inter-looping of yarns or inter-meshing of loops. Single jersey is weft knitted cloth which is shaped by single set of needles. Single jersey is the frequently recycled for manufacture T-shirts in textile. In single jersey face side and back side look is dissimilar[2]. This cloth is much warm, elastic, flexible, and wear to luxury therefore get acceptance. There are dual basic variations of knit cloth weft-knit and warp-knit cloth. Weft Knitting is a technique of founding a cloth in which the loops are made in horizontal way from a single yarn and intermeshing of loops take place in a round or flat form on crosswise wise basis[3]. Warp Knitting is a process of creating a textile in which the loops are made in perpendicular way along the distance of the cloth from each warp yarns and intermeshing of loops take place in a flat form of length wise base. The duration shrinkage can only be defined as a modification in the sizes of a cloth or apparel. This dimensional alteration may be in a positive (growth) or negative (shrinkage) way for cloth length, width, and width. Shrinkage is one of the most serious problems of the knitted fabrics[4]. Specially, it is create in S/J knitted plain fabrics. Because of different face and back side of the S/J fabrics continuously incline to create twisting. Therefore, shrinkage is designed in single jersey frequently, where the additional fabrics like dual jersey are not so affected significantly as associated with it. Shrinkage makes sewing problem which resultant seam pucker. Social feels distress due to uniform of shrink cloth. Spirality rises from twist tension in the ingredient's yarns of basic fabric, producing all loops to change and throwing the cloth wales and courses into an angular connection other than 90 grade[5]. Separately from this, spirality is additional serious problem for single jersey knitted cloths due to their irregular loop foundation. Bursting strength is an important property of knitted fabrics. These fabrics have to pass many processes like dyeing and finishing. So they need enough strength to resist the force applied on it during different processing stages. Fabric abrasion and pilling are also a problem for knitted fabrics[6]. If pills are formed on the fabric surface, it looks unattractive in appearance. Numerous investigates were achieved to investigate the effect of different knitting strictures on the physical and mechanical properties of knitted cloths[7]. This study is investigated Effects of variable parameters Count,

Stitch Length on GSM, Shrinkage, Spirality, Bursting Strength, Pilling of unfinished Single Jersey Knit Cloth” was observed.

Materials and methods

Raw materials: In this project cotton knitted samples were tested. Yarn of different counts produced in Tania Spinning Mills ltd, yarn produced from 100% cotton. Cotton knitted single jersey samples were used with variable count & also different stitch lengths. The details of the samples were as follows; the samples were weft knitted single jersey plain fabric with 2.70 mm, 2.75 mm, and 2.80 mm stitch length. Yarn count used 24Ne, 28Ne, 30Ne combed ring yarn which is shown below in table 1.

Count	Stitch Length (mm)
24Ne	2.70
	2.75
	2.80
28Ne	2.70
	2.75
	2.80
30Ne	2.70
	2.75
	2.80

Yarn from the equal lot is located in the creels sensibly for knitting. Subsequently knitting the sample remained dried in relaxed state and then managed that comprises conditioning of the cloths at 65% relative humidity & 30 °C ± 2 °C. After relaxation the following test were carried out at 27°C ± 2 °C & 65% RH. Finally the entire test GSM, Shrinkage, Spirality, Bursting Strength, Pilling was completed.

Result & Discussion

Effect on Bursting Strength

Specific data analysis for constant count

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	Bursting Test (KPa)
24Ne	2.70	486
	2.75	453
	2.80	459

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	Bursting Test (KPa)
28Ne	2.70	378
	2.75	398
	2.80	356

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	Bursting Test (KPa)
30 Ne	2.70	319
	2.75	326
	2.80	300

When the count (Ne) increases the bursting strength will be decreased gradually.
Specific data analysis for constant stitch length

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Bursting Test (KPa)
2.70	24	486
	28	378
	30	319

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Bursting Test (KPa)
2.75	24	453
	28	398
	30	326

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Bursting Test (KPa)
2.80	24	459
	28	356
	30	300

From the above graph we see that for constant stitch length by increasing the count the bursting strength is decreasing.

Effect on Shrinkage %

Specific data analysis for constant count

Count	Stitch Length (mm)	Shrinkage% (Length Wise)
24Ne	2.70	-7.66
	2.75	-8.83
	2.80	-10.16

Count	Stitch Length (mm)	Shrinkage% (Length Wise)
28Ne	2.70	-13.0
	2.75	-12.5
	2.80	-11.16

Count	Stitch Length (mm)	Shrinkage% (Length Wise)
30Ne	2.70	-14.16
	2.75	-14.0
	2.80	-16.95

From the above graph we see that for constant count by increasing the stitch length the shrinkage % is decreasing & the fabric length is increasing.

Specific data analysis for constant stitch length

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Shrinkage% (Length Wise)
2.70	24	-7.66
	28	-13
	30	-14.16

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Shrinkage% (Length Wise)
2.75	24	-8.83
	28	-12.5
	30	-14

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Shrinkage% (Length Wise)
2.80	24	-10.16
	28	-11.16
	30	-16.95

From the above graph we see that for constant stitch length by increasing the count the shrinkage % is decreasing & the fabric length is increasing.

Specific data analysis for constant count

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	Shrinkage% (Width Wise)
24Ne	2.70	+0.5
	2.75	+1.5
	2.80	+3.0

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	Shrinkage% (Width Wise)
28Ne	2.70	+2.5
	2.75	+0.83
	2.80	+1.0

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	Shrinkage% (Width Wise)
30Ne	2.70	+3.83
	2.75	+4.5
	2.80	+7.83

From the above graph we see that for constant count by increasing the stitch length the shrinkage% is increasing & fabric width is decreasing.

Specific data analysis for constant stitch length

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Shrinkage% (Width Wise)
2.70	24	+0.5
	28	+2.5
	30	+3.83

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Shrinkage% (Width Wise)
2.75	24	+1.5
	28	+0.83
	30	+4.5

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Shrinkage% (Width Wise)
2.80	24	+3.0
	28	+1.0
	30	+7.83

From the above graph we see that for constant stitch length by increasing the count the shrinkage% is increasing & fabric width is shrinking.

Effect on Spirality

Specific data analysis for constant count

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	Spirality %
24Ne	2.70	3.97
	2.75	4.35
	2.80	6.82

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	Spirality %
28Ne	2.70	5.62
	2.75	5.62
	2.80	7.31

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	Spirality %
30Ne	2.70	4.76
	2.75	9.30
	2.80	7.74

From the above graph we see that for constant count by increasing the stitch length the spirality% is increasing.

Specific data analysis for constant stitch length

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Spirality %
2.70	24	3.97
	28	5.62
	30	4.76

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Spirality %
2.75	24	4.35
	28	5.62
	30	9.30

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Spirality %
2.80	24	6.82
	28	7.31
	30	7.74

From the above graph we see that for constant stitch length by increasing the count the spirality% is increasing.

Effect on GSM

Specific data analysis for constant count

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	GSM
24Ne	2.70	200
	2.75	178
	2.80	175

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	GSM
28Ne	2.70	154
	2.75	151
	2.80	154

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	GSM
30Ne	2.70	144
	2.75	148
	2.80	140

From the above graph we see that for constant count by increasing the Stitch Length the GSM is decreasing.

Specific data analysis for constant stitch length

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	GSM
2.70	24	200
	28	154
	30	144

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	GSM
2.75	24	178
	28	151
	30	148

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	GSM
2.80	24	175
	28	154
	30	140

From the above graph we see that for constant count by increasing the Stitch Length the GSM is decreasing.

Effect on Pilling

Specific data analysis for constant count

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	Pilling Test
24Ne	2.70	4~5
	2.75	3
	2.80	3~4

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	Pilling Test
28Ne	2.70	4
	2.75	3~4
	2.80	4

Count (Ne)	Stitch Length (mm)	Pilling Test
30Ne	2.70	3~4
	2.75	4
	2.80	3~4

From the above graph we see that for constant count by increasing the stitch length the pilling illustrate lower grade.

Specific data analysis for constant stitch length

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Pilling Test
2.70	24	4~5
	28	4
	30	3~4

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Pilling Test
2.75	24	3
	28	3~4
	30	4

Stitch Length (mm)	Count (Ne)	Pilling Test
2.80	24	3~4
	28	4
	30	3~4

From the above graph we see that for constant stitch length by increasing the count the pilling illustrate also lower grade.

Conclusion

It is clear that GSM increases with the decrease of yarn count. As the finer yarn gives tighter fabric structure that's why shrinkage reduced gradually by using finer yarn. Mostly stitch length and count shows a vital role in Single jersey knit cloth. From the above mentioned statistics it has been recognized that when stitch length and count Increases then the GSM will be reduced. Here yarn count and stitch length both are variables. From the investigation, it also gives knowledge approximately grey stage of knit cloths, that source will show better performance for the good selection of count and stitch length for correct physical properties. In this research work, the effects of count & stitch length on plain single jersey fabrics were investigated. Among the various properties, GSM, Shrinkage, Spirality, Bursting Strength, Pilling resistance were examined. A significant change was observed for the various count & stitch lengths. When the GSM decrease with the increase of count & stitch length. Spirality and shrinkage increase but bursting strength decreases with the increase of count & stitch length. Pilling resistance illustrate lower grade with the increase of count & stitch length.

References

- [1] Spencer, D.J., Knitting technology: a comprehensive handbook and practical guide. 2001: Woodhead Publishing.
- [2] Tou, N.A., An investigation of arcing in two structure weft knit fabrics. 2005.
- [3] Sayed, Z.B., et al., Effect of knitted structures and yarn count on the properties of weft knitted fabrics. *Journal of Textile Science and Technology*, 2018. 4(2): p. 67-77.
- [4] Cao, H., et al., Bi-stretch auxetic woven fabrics based on foldable geometry. *Textile Research Journal*, 2019. 89(13): p. 2694-2712.
- [5] Pavko-Čuden, A., Skewness and Spirality of Knitted Structures Poševnost in spiralnost pletiv.
- [6] Akter, S., M.A. Al Faruque, and M.M. Islam, Effect of Stitch Length on Different Properties of Plain Single Jersey Fabric. *International Journal Of Modern Engineering Research*, 2017. 7: p. 71-75.
- [7] Fatkić, E., J. Geršak, and D. Ujević, Influence of knitting parameters on the mechanical properties of plain jersey weft knitted fabrics. *Fibres & Textiles in Eastern Europe*, 2011. 19(5): p. 88.

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